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Assessment of Availability and Utilisation of Online Platforms in Christian Religion Education in Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria

MAKINDE, Oluwasegun Faith

Department of Christian Religious Studies, Caleb University, Imota, Lagos State

ONI, Timothy Olamide

Department of Christian Religious Studies Caleb University, Imota, Lagos State

AKINYERA, Abideen Tope

Directorate of General Studies Abraham Adesanya Polytechnic, Ijebu-Igbo

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ABSTRACT: The study assessed the availability and utilisation of online platforms and platforms in Christian Religion Education in Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria. Inadequate provision and utilisation of new technology facilities by teachers could result in producing graduates with only theoretical knowledge and less experience in practical courses which required the application of ICT skills. A Christian Religion Education is considered a veritable instrument for preparing students for development of a solid moral foundation based on Christian values and encourages them to navigate complex ethical dilemmas in their personal and professional lives. A descriptive survey research design was used. A sample of 200 students of Christian Religion Education through a random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data which were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer research questions. The findings of the study revealed that there are online platforms and resources accessible and they are used by both lecturers (instructors) and students in christian religion education programmes. It was therefore recommended that teaching and learning of Christian Religion Education in tertiary institutions should be encouraged by the Nigeria government and ensure that online platforms and resources are supplied and made available.

KEYWORDS: Online Platforms and Resources, Availability, Utilisation, Instructional Delivery, Christian Religion Education

INTRODUCTION

Christian Religious Education is a field of study that systematically examines Christian faith as contained in Old Testament and New Testament components of the Bible; requiring both synchronous and asynchronous mode of online platforms and resources. The advent of the digital era has resulted in the transformation of technologies in everyday life. Many educational system have transformed from offline to online, allowing them to gain new development opportunities. The swift transformation of ICT and its associated technology over the past few decades has had a noteworthy influence on the transformation of various facets of teacher. The integration of emerging technologies in teaching and learning process is no longer a choice but a need due to; the changing learning environment, demand for flexibility in methodology, and the need to enhance creativity and productivity in learning (Onyema, 2019).

Online platform has revolutionized learning for several years, improving efficiencies, workflow and collaboration. The minimum criteria or expectations that must be considered in higher education in order to transform face-to-face courses into online or e-learning environments include focusing on online capabilities developed by both students and teachers, considering the intentional integration of technology to support teaching and learning processes, and emphasizing active learning (learner-centred) and/or problem solving-based approaches (Ferrufino Olmos, 2021). In recent years, the adoption of online platforms in Nigeria has gained momentum (Ogwu, Emelogu, Azor, & Okwo, 2023). With the proliferation of internet connectivity, particularly in urban areas, students and educators are increasingly embracing digital technologies to facilitate learning. Online platforms and resources may provide a wide range of educational resources, interactive tools, and collaborative spaces that could empower christian religious educators to engage with educational content at their own pace and convenience. These platforms and resources can offer flexible learning environments, enabling students to balance their studies with other commitments, and have the potential to democratize education by reaching underserved populations (Rambe & Moeti (2017).

Christian religious educators may employ online platforms and resources such as social media platforms and virtual event platforms, computers, power-point presentation package to teach and learn at different intensities and levels according to their comfort zones. Information posted on the social media and virtual event platforms can be easily modified and updated to serve teaching and learning more effectively of christian religious studies. The researcher observed that most of christain religion education lecturers have no computer education knowledge because it was not

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entrenched in the curriculum at their primary or secondary school level. Due to its ability to reduce the time and stress of long, boring sessions and allow students to study at their own pace, online platforms and resources should be available for Christian Religion Education lecturers (instructors) and students. Hence, the needs to assess availability and utilisation of online platforms and resources in christian religion education in Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

It seems that few Nigerian higher institutions have exploited online platforms and resources for teaching and learning, despite their importance. Research on using online platforms and resources for instruction appears to be lacking, for starters. Not having enough computers for technological proficiency seems to be another issue. Therefore, it would be difficult for instructors and students in Christian religious education who are not computer literate to get used to using online materials and platforms in the classroom. In the meantime, the effectiveness and efficiency of Christian education curriculum implementation depend on online platforms and resources. However, the lack of physical technology such as computers, computer laboratories, internet, teleconferencing equipment, digital libraries, and digital classrooms makes it difficult to use online platforms and resources in developing countries like Nigeria. The researcher observed that many of the CRS instructors are also unaware of the availability and utilisation of online platforms and utilisation. The problem is that the new technologies raise questions about the availability and use of online materials and platforms in educational institutions for teaching Christian religion studies. In light of this, the current study sought to determine the extent of availability and utilisation of online platforms and resources in Christian Religious Education at Lagos State University.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to assess the availability and utilisation of online platforms and resources in Christian Religious Education in Lagos State University. Specifically, this research aims to :

- i. ascertain the availability of online platforms and resources for Christian Religion Education at Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria.
- ii. ascertain the level of usage of online platforms and resources by lecturers of the Christian Religion Education in Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. What is the level of availability of online platforms and resources for Christian Religion Education at Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent is the usage of online platforms and resources for lecturers of the Christian Religion Education in Lagos State University, Ojo, Nigeria?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview of Christian Religious Education

Conceptually, Christian Religious Studies refers to the systematic study of Christian faith as contained in the Old Testament and New Testament of the Holy Bible (Baiyeri, 2010). The Federal Government of Nigeria stipulates that “instruction at all levels has to be oriented towards inculcating moral and spiritual principle in interpersonal and human relations” (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2004). Hence, Christian Religious Studies has been approved by the National Policy of Education (NPE) as one of the subjects to be taught and studied in primary and secondary school in Nigeria (NPE, 2013). Ilori (2013) asserted that Christian Religious Education (CRE) holds a significant place in the educational landscape of Nigeria, a country with a diverse cultural and religious heritage. Christian religious education is component of the holistic-oriented education, by means of which the student is led towards progressive habitualization for social duties towards the community to which he belongs and in which he has a share (Okeke, 2011).

Simply put, the purpose of Christian religious education is to effect integral formation. This integral human formation includes holistic, developmental, social and personal harmony (Okeke, 2011). Rooted in the nation's colonial history, CRE has been an integral part of the curriculum in Nigerian schools. However, in recent years, debates have emerged regarding its relevance and impact on students' holistic development. Historically, the introduction of Christian Religious Education in Nigerian schools dates back to the colonial era when British missionaries established schools to propagate Christianity alongside formal education. Over time, CRE became institutionalized in the curriculum, reflecting the dominant religious identity of the colonial powers. Post-independence, Nigeria adopted a secular constitution, but CRE retained its place in schools, reflecting the country's religious diversity.

Objectives of Teaching Christian Religion in Nigerian Schools

The following objectives of teaching religions in schools:

- i. To provide more opportunity for the Nigerian studentss, to learn more about God and thereby develop their faith in him.
- ii. To acquaint the students with the broad outlines of Islam and Christianity.
- iii. To give the students adequate intellectual exposure that will enable them pursue further education in Religious Studies.
- iv. To help the studentss to understand the basic teachings of God/Allah and to apply these to their daily lives and work.
- v. To develop in the studentss moral values such as humility, respect, love, kindness, justice and fair play, spirit of forgiveness, obedience, devotion to duty, orderly behaviour and selfless service to God and humanity.

Concept of Online Platforms and Resources

Online platforms is a unifying term used to describe the use of online learning, web-based training and technology delivered instructions. It is simply called Electronic Learning. It involves learning using groups on social media such as WhatsApp (WA), telegram, Zoom applications, or other social media to ensure that students can learn at the same time and in different places (Salehudin et al 2021). Mohammed and Yarinchi (2013) noted that ICT has taken a prominent collaborative position as a tool for various creativities in education. It is equally serving as a catalyst in modifying teaching and learning activities to the advantage of both teachers and learners in the learning environment. Teachers can only effectively integrate technology in their instruction if they are themselves knowledgeable about the technology (Buabeng-Andoh, 2012). Part of the drive

towards greater use of modern technology in education is equipping teachers and learners of today with skills that will enable them to use such technologies that will expose them to experiences that will help them to think and act globally (Laleye, 2019).

Online platforms and resources involves learning using groups on social media such as WhatsApp (WA), telegram, Zoom applications, or other platforms to ensure that students can learn at the same time and in different places. It is an innovative approach to the delivery of educational services via electronic in the form of information that enhances the knowledge, skills and other outcomes of students. Online platforms and resources is implemented through a network connection. It is a form of learning that involves the use of information and communication technology through a computer (PC) or laptop connected to an internet (Horton & Horton, 2003). The method of teaching needs to be complemented, more especially in the era of ICTs, where the role of a teacher has shifted from being the key source of information and transmitter of knowledge to that of becoming a collaborator and co-learner (Samaila, Makinde,& Zambwa, 2016).

Availability and Utilisation of Social Media Platforms

Social media is an online platform used to share information and turn communication into interactive dialogue with internal or external audiences. Ogbe (2014) defined social media as “the new media that speed up conversations in a more interactive way that makes communication more effective and worthwhile. It is an online media that takes communication beyond the limitations of the traditional media, which most often delivers content but does not allow the reader, or as the case may be, viewers or listeners, to participate in the or development of the content”. McFarland and Ployhart (2015) simply defined social media as —digital Web 2.0 platforms that facilitate information sharing, user-created content, and collaboration across people. Oseni, Dingley, and Hart (2018) that grouped social media into only two categories: online social network services (SNS) or online social networks (ONS) and instant messaging (IM) apps. On most occasions, the term—social medial is used interchangeably with — online social network services.

Nations (2021) saw social media as “web-based communication tools that enable people to interact with each other by sharing and consuming information.” Nations definition, although simple, portrayed in simple terms the very essence of social media, which is the primary aim of sharing and consuming. Abdullah et al. (2015) affirms that the interactive aura of the new media confers an unprecedented popularity on them and the ubiquity of the social networking sites within their short period of arrival is unparallel in the annals of media industry. The popularity of social networking sites has affected our social interaction in different ways as we adapt to our increasingly technological world (Edegoh, 2012). The way web users interact and talk to each other has changed and will continue to change. These users now socialize through the internet and it takes away from the person socialization that has been around forever.

- i. **Facebook:** Facebook is a popular free social online platforms that allows registered users to create profiles, upload photos and video, send messages and keep in touch with friends, family and colleagues. Founded in 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg, the site is free to members and derives its revenue from ads. The name comes from the paper document with names and faces issued to freshmen to help them get acquainted with each other. Using the search facilities, members can locate other Facebook members and “friend” them by sending them an invitation, or they can invite people to join Facebook. It has public features such as; Timeline/Wall—The Timeline (new format) or Wall (old format) is the area on Facebook where members post comments and their current status and location as well as upload photos and videos.
- ii. **Whatsapp Messenger:** This is a online platform instant messaging application that allows iPhone, BlackBerry, Android, and Windows Phone users to exchange text, image, and audio messeages for free. Founded in 2009 by Brian Acton and Jan Koum, WhatsApp uses the Internet as an alternative to the SMS text messaging system. WhatsApp also provides voice calling from one WhatsApp user to the other, as well as voice recording, which lets users record and send audio messages instead of typing.
- iii. **Tiktok:** This is a online video sharing app where users can create videos of up to one minute in length. It features a "for users page" with content that is carefully curated for each user based off of their interactions on the app. Users can use hashtags, tag people, and even go live on the app as a way to interact with one another. TikTok is changing social media in a remarkable way.
- iv. **Telegram Messenger:** This is commonly known as Telegram, is a online platform instant messaging (IM) service. It was originally launched for iOS on 14 August 2013 and Android in October 2013. It allows users to exchange messages, share media and files, hold private and group voice or video calls, as well as public livestreams. It is available for Android, iOS, Windows, macOS, Linux, and web browsers. Telegram provides end-to-end encryption in voice and video calls, and in optional private chats, which Telegram calls Secret Chats.

The use of social media is on a very high increase in contemporary society, especially among students. Hence, social media statistics in Nigeria according to Statcounter (2020), reports have it that social media has higher rate users such as Facebook 49.22%; Twitter 26.8%; Pinterest 11.7%; Instagram 10.04%; You Tube1.86%; LinkedIn 0.22%. From the statistics, it shows that social media has become a prominent part of student's lives as they are more concerned with Facebook friends, videos on YouTube posts, tweets, and other online communication than they are with face-to-face friends which is disheartening to note; hence creating a nearby communication gap. This made Singh, Amiri and Sabbarwal (2017), to note that this day, students are the most users of social media. It made available the platform for them to build social networks or social relations among themselves.

Availibilty and Utilisation of Virtual Event Platform

“Virtual events are not the same as virtual worlds; they are not web conferencing, but are a result of the new virtual event platforms and software tools that have become available” (Pearlman & Gates, 2010). A virtual event platforms allows an individual to experience the event online without gathering in person. Virtual events can be classified into virtual conferences and summits, webcast events, webinars, e-learning events, podcasts, online radio, live and virtual hybrid events, and live streaming (Evans, 2020). For attendees, virtual events allow for free access from remote locations, and they are not controlled by the boundaries of their geographical location (Pearlman & Gates, 2010), which also reduces travelling costs (Cvent, 2020). Since the individuals cannot see one another in significant events, it is complicated to form biases against people in terms of race, gender, or age, which leads to less discrimination among the attendees and increased comfort (Rheingold, 2008). Virtual events allow them to visit and explore an event without the fear of contracting the deadly disease.

- i. **Google Hangouts:** This is one of the video conferencing systems available through Google Plus (Duffy, 2013). Google Hangouts is similar to Skype, as it provides a free audio/video conference along with a text chat capability. Both programs offer a free mobile app, making it easy for iPad, iPhone, or Android users to access the programs. However, Google Hangouts also has other unique features. Anyone who has Google Plus accounts can join the group conference. Video conferencing on Google Hangouts can be recorded and uploaded to YouTube for sharing. The user can decide whether to share video conferencing publicly or only with friends. In addition, Google Hangouts also allows screen captures, screen shares, and remote desktop control, allowing users to control a computer monitor from the other end of the room during the video conferencing (Google Inc., 2013).
- ii. **Zoom:** Zoom application is an American communications Technology Company headquartered in San Jose, California that provides video telephone and online chat services through a cloud-based peer-to-peer software platform and is used for teleconferencing, telecommuting, full-time education, part-time education, distance education, and social relations. It is an open source as it is readily available for use on the market (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2020). Among other factors, many could have chosen the Zoom application because it has now become the leader in educational sector and modern enterprise video and audio communications, with an easy, reliable cloud platform for video and audio conferencing, chat and webinars across mobile, desk, and room system (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2020).

Virtual learning also helps to relate school experiences to work practices, creates economic viability for workers, in order to contribute to the total development of the institution, strengthens teaching and learning and provides opportunities for connections between the school and the world (Cellini, 2021). Virtual enhances enhances teaching and learning through its dynamic interactive and engaging content and provides real opportunities for individualization of instruction. It also uses potentials to accelerate, enriches and deepens skills, motivate and engage students' learning.

Availability and Utilisation of Power-point Presentations

Power point is ideal for producing full-screen computer presentations to enhance lectures, demonstrations and displays. It can enhance the effectiveness of classroom lectures by highlighting key points, providing pictures and other graphics supporting the material (Jeremiah, 2013). Every day more than 30 million presentations are delivered with power-point (Ramon et al., 2013) aimed at meeting the needs of the everchanging learners' demands. This has led to a gradual shift from the conventional/traditional teaching methods to learners' friendly and ICT based methodologies.

Using power-point presentations may encourage students' participation in the class and improve their achievement. It enhances learning by providing a better understanding and comprehension of the subjects as well as by providing different approaches, methods, and techniques for ease of understanding by the learners. This variety of techniques, which can be on the same slide; like adding pictures, sounds, colors, and animations combines all kinds of learners (kinesthetic, auditory, and visual) and give them all the chance to be active learners and raise their interest in learning. This also has an outstanding effect in teaching and learning of CRS and information retention. The conventional/traditional method of teaching Christian Religious Studies has been found to present many challenges in the teaching learning process, such as keeping the students passive in class, which invariably leads to poor academic achievement and retention (Weimer, 2012).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Pew Research Center (2021), which report that Facebook has more overall users than other platforms. Based on the overall findings, social media should be incorporated into higher education institutions marking plans. If universities are limited to one platform, Facebook would be the top choice. The Pew Research Center (2023) reports the average age of Facebook users to be significantly higher than that of Instagram users, with the majority of young adults using Instagram and TikTok. Based on this, institutions may prioritize Instagram over Facebook. However, findings from this study suggest that for recruitment purposes, Facebook demonstrates higher engagement than Instagram. Therefore, educational institutions aiming to maximize their outreach should ensure that Facebook is part of their recruitment strategy.

Galan et al. (2015) found that postgraduate students turned to social media to learn about student life, job opportunities, and potential fields of study.

Nasrullah, Djadir and Mifta (2021) who carried out study on effect of implementing online learning with the Zoom platform on students' learning outcomes. The results of inferential statistical analysis show that students' average score after online learning using Zoom application is greater.

Abdulmoneim (2018) who investigates effect of using some google educational applications in teaching computer curriculum on the achievement of students for the first year in College of Education, University of Samarra. It was revealed that there was statistical significant differences at the scores of the experimental group and the scores of control group students in the post-achievement test for the experimental group studied using some Google educational applications in favour of Google educational applications.

Nurwati, Asdar, Nasrullah, Djadir and Mifta (2021) on effect of implementing online learning with the Zoom platform on students' learning outcome. The results of inferential statistical analysis show that students' average score after online learning using Zoom is greater.

Abdulmoneim (2018) who investigates effect of using some google educational applications in teaching computer curriculum on the achievement of students for the first year in College of Education, University of Samarra. It was revealed that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance (0.05) between the mean scores of the experimental group and the scores of the control group students in the post-achievement test for the experimental group studied using some Google educational applications.

Jimoh, Shahid, Ibrahim and Usman (2020) who carried out study on effects of video instructional types on retention and achievement level of senior secondary school students in mathematics in Minna, Niger state. It was revealed that there was significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught mathematics using Text Animation and narration, Text and Animation, Text and Narration and Text Only video instructional types.

Ogwunte et al (2020) in their research work Perceived Influence of Zoom Cloud and Whatsapp Technologies on Instructional Delivery in University Business Education Classroom in Rivers State their result reveals that zoom cloud technology offers educators with the ability to

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communicate in real time with dispersed students via computers and mobile phones, ability to secure record and store sessions without recourse to third party software, ability to create users specific authentication, ability to create real time encryption of meetings, ability to back up recording to online remote server network, ability to connect synchronously with students over videos and audios, ability to share screen and ability for students to work in group. The study also perceived Influence of Whatsapp Technology on Instructional Delivery in University Business Education Classroom that whatsapp technology offers educators with the ability to connect with their students, share ideas, share pictures, share messages and information of interests, ability to construct a public profile within a bounded system, ability to connect semi public profile within a bounded system, ability to provide message with images which are more effective for students learning, ability to instantly send messages to anywhere in the world and ability to provide audio and video callings.

Ofilu (2016) revealed that the experimental group taught with power point presentation performed better than the control group taught using conventional method with a significant difference in favour of the experimental group.

The study of Gambari, Yusuf and Balogun (2015) found out that students taught with power point performed better than those taught with chalkboard method with a significant different in favour of the power point instructional package.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a descriptive survey design. The population for this study was christian education students at the Lagos State University, Ojo. The sample size for the study was 200 christian education students. The data for this study were collected through the use of a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument for data collection was subjected to face and validity by experts in Christian Education. The instrument was administered by the researcher with the aid of research assistants using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Online platforms and resources available to enhance the Christian Religion Education programmes taught in Lagos State University.

S/N	Items	Means	SD
1.	Zoom	4.40	0.534
2.	Facebook	4.25	1.592
3.	Power-point	4.60	0.893
4.	Computer	3.90	0.519
5.	Whatsapp	4.98	1.600
	Grand Mean	4.43	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 showed the responses to items 1-5, the mean ratings as well as the standard deviation. The mean ratings of the items ranged from 3.90 to 4.98 which implies that there are high number of online platforms that are available for utilisation of teaching Christian Religion Education programme in LASU (Grand mean 4.43). The standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.519 to 1.600. The grand mean of 4.98 implies that online platforms are available for utilisation to a high extent for the effective teaching and learning of Christain Religion Education programme in LASU.

Table 2: Lecturers use of online platforms and resources to enhance Christian Religion Education programmes teaching an learning in Lagos State University.

S/N	Items	Means	SD
1.	A significant proportion of lecturers in tertiary institutions are incorporating online platforms and resources into their teaching practices for christian religion education. Utilising platforms like zoom app, google meet to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.	4.13	0.930
2.	The usage of online platforms has led to a noticeable shift in teaching methodologies among christian religious lecturers. With a trend towards more interactive and student-centred learning experiences.	4.00	0.740
3.	Despite several challenges, including lack of adequate training, and resistance to change lecturers still make use of online platforms and resources to teach.	4.20	0.519
4.	The utilisation of resources like laptops and powerpoint enhanced accessibility to online platforms and foster improved academic performances .	4.38	0.921
5.	Lecturers frequently employ online platforms and resources as part of their routine teaching activities, with many using these tools for a variety of purposes such as delivering lecturers, distributing course materials, conducting quizzes and facilitating group projects and discussion	4.19	1.800
	Grand Mean	4.18	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 shows the responses to items 5 - 10, the mean ratings as well as the standard deviation. The mean ratings of items ranged from 4.00 to 4.80 which implies that lecturers use the available online platforms and resources for teaching and learning of christian religion education in LASU (Grand mean = 4.18). The standard deviation of the items ranged from 0.519 to 1.800. The grand mean of 4.18 implies that the respondents generally agreed that lecturers make good use of online platforms and resources that are available for utilisation to a high extent for the effective teaching and learning of Christian Religious Education programmes in LASU.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of the study showed that online platforms and resources were moderately available (mean = 4.43) for teaching and learning of christian religious education programmes in the sampled university in Lagos State. This finding is in line to the study of Ogwunte et al (2020) in their research work Perceived Influence of Zoom Cloud and Whatsapp Technologies on Instructional Delivery in University Business Education Classroom in Rivers State their result reveals that zoom cloud technology offers educators with the ability to communicate in real time with dispersed students via computers and mobile phones, ability to secure record and store sessions without recourse to third party software, ability to create users specific authentication, ability to create real time encryption of meetings, ability to back up recording to online remote server network, ability to connect synchronously with students over videos and audios, ability to share screen and ability for students to work in group. Brahma (2020) which stated that the use of Zoom as an online based learning in Sociology and Anthropology subjects for the students majoring in Citizenship Education at STKIP Kusumanegara Jakarta result showed that Sociology and Anthropology courses become more interactive and in demand by students because the online learning media used are very innovative and effective according to the current development. Through zoom, lecturers and students can conduct video conference which is used as a means of communicating in online learning and the recordings made during the meeting are more secure.

The finding of the study showed that lecturers make good use of online platforms and resources that are available moderately for instructional delivery (mean = 4.18). This finding is collaborated by that of Galan et al. (2015) found that postgraduate students turned to social media to learn about student life, job opportunities, and potential fields of study. Ofili (2016) revealed that the experimental group taught with power point presentation performed better than the control group taught using conventional method with a significant difference in favour of the experimental group. The study of Gambari, Yusuf and Balogun (2015) found out that students taught with power point performed better than those taught with chalkboard method with a significant different in favour of the power point instructional package.

CONCLUSION

In the contemporary educational landscape, the advent of digital technologies has transformed the way instruction is delivered across disciplines, including Christian Religious Education (CRE). At Lagos State University (LASU), the integration of online platforms and resources—such as social media, virtual event platforms, PowerPoint presentations, and computers—has significantly enhanced both accessibility and engagement in CRE instruction. The availability of online platforms is a pivotal factor in the educational process at LASU. With the widespread integration of the internet into daily activities, students and educators have unprecedented access to vast repositories of knowledge. Social media platforms like Whatsapp and Telegram serve not only as channels for communication but also as forums for discussion and discourse on religious themes and current events. Educators can create dedicated groups or pages where students engage in discussions, share relevant articles, and reflect on spiritual topics, thus fostering a sense of community even outside the classroom.

Additionally, virtual event platforms such as Zoom, Microsoft Teams, and Google Meet have become commonplace for conducting lectures, seminars, and discussions. These tools allow educators to reach students who might not be able to attend physical classes—either due to location or scheduling conflicts—enhancing inclusivity. The pedagogical techniques utilized in CRE instruction have naturally adapted to leverage these available online resources. PowerPoint presentations are a staple in educational contexts, and they have found enhanced utility in the virtual classroom. Instructors at LASU use PowerPoint not only for delivering structured content but also for incorporating multimedia elements such as videos, images, and sound clips that can illustrate Biblical teachings and religious practices. This multisensory approach caters to various learning styles, making the educational experience more engaging and effective.

Moreover, the shift to remote learning necessitated by global circumstances has led educators to become increasingly adept at using these tools. Continuous professional development and training on digital literacy are paramount; many instructors at LASU are now using tutorials and online courses to improve their technological competencies, allowing them to facilitate smoother online interactions. This professionalization enhances instructional delivery, ensuring that students receive a robust educational experience despite the challenges posed by traditional learning environments.

Despite the advantages, there are notable challenges in the utilization of these online platforms. Issues such as internet connectivity, access to personal computers or smartphones, and digital literacy lag among some students can hinder the full realization of online education's potential. Therefore, it is crucial for the institution to explore partnerships with tech companies, ensuring that all students have the necessary resources to participate fully. Looking ahead, future initiatives could focus on blending online and traditional instruction—often referred to as hybrid learning. Such models could leverage the strengths of both modalities, ensuring that CRE instruction at LASU remains relevant and impactful.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings the following recommendations are advanced thus:

- i. Well-standard dedicated ICT laboratories should be built in universities and students should be allowed to have easy access to them.
- ii. Lecturers should make use of social media to disseminate knowledge/instructions.
- iii. The contents align with the educational objectives and curriculum requirements in effectively engagement students.

- iv. Students should adopt a disciplined approach to social media usage, using it as a source of reputable information for academic objectives in order to effectively improve their academic performance.

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